

The effect of renewable energy transition on the thermal comfort in a pig farm – animal compartment level experimental investigation

Petros Demissie Tegenaw¹, Manon Everaert^{1,2}, Marijke Aluwé¹, Steven Lecompte², Jarissa Maselyne¹

¹ ILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Merelbeke, Belgium

² UGENT (Ghent University), Ghent, Belgium

Renewable energy integration in livestock farming is crucial for curbing CO₂ emissions, with on-farm energy consumption being a significant contributor. The RES4LIVE project, funded by the EU Horizon 2020 program, aims to diminish fossil fuel dependency in livestock farms. As part of this project, a modular heat pump was installed at a farrow-to-finish pig farm in Melle, Belgium. The system consists of a low and a high temperature heat pump with an overall heating capacity of 60 kW. The primary heat source for this system is thermal energy from photovoltaic thermal collectors (PVT). In total, there are 24 flat plate PVT panels installed at the farm, offering an electrical capacity of 8.40 kW and a thermal capacity of 32.8 kW. The integrated installation of the modular heat pump and the PVT panels is planned to deliver the whole heating demand of the farm (220 MWh per year), and replaces an existing gas boiler. Thermal energy from the heat pump is conveyed to the farm using water as a heat transfer medium. This water circulates through a network of pipes, distributing heat to various systems such as sanitary water lines, air heaters, and underfloor heating. Notably, the air heater lines and underfloor heating play a crucial role in heating the animal compartments. In this study, an examination is conducted on the temperatures within the animal compartments when the heat pump serves as the primary heating source, compared to the gas boiler. The data encompasses 16 fattening, 2 farrowing, and 3 weaned pig compartments, with their respective temperatures measured by Pt1000 sensors and logged every 10 minutes. The operational period of the heat pump spans from January 25th to February 5th, 2024, forming the basis of this experimental investigation. The findings underscore the effectiveness of the integrated heat pump and PVT system in reducing carbon emissions and offering a viable alternative to fossil fuel-based gas boilers on the farm.